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THE MAIN FACTORS FOR EDUCATIONAL TOURISM MARKET DEVELOPMENT OF UKRAINE

ОСНОВНІ ФАКТОРИ РОЗВИТКУ РИНКУ ОСВІТНЬОГО ТУРИЗМУ УКРАЇНИ

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Гутарева Ю.В., Коваленко А.Б. Основні фактори розвитку ринку освітнього туризму України. Оглядова стаття.

У статті розглянуті основні фактори, що впливають на розвиток ринку освітнього туризму України. Визначено місце освітнього туризму України на міжнародному ринку освітнього туризму. Досліджено основні мотиви освітнього туризму України. Визначено специфічні особливості освітнього туризму та види освітнього туризму. Сформульовано авторське визначення освітнього туризму як економічної категорії. Розроблено авторську модель освітнього туризму, що базується на поняттях «освіта» та «туризм». Охарактеризовано найважливіші передумови, що визначають обставини розвитку ринку освітнього туризму. Також виділено актуальні проблеми освітнього туризму України. Розроблено шляхи удосконалення освітнього туризму України та надані рекомендації щодо покращення даної категорії туризму.

Ключові слова: туризм, освітній туризм, ринок освітнього туризму, фактор, перспективи, розвиток

Hutareva Yu.V., Kovalenko A.B. The Main Factors for Educational Tourism Market Development of Ukraine. Review article.

The article deals with the main factors that influence the Ukrainian educational tourism market development. The place of educational tourism of Ukraine in the international market of educational tourism has been determined. The main motives of educational tourism of Ukraine have been investigated. Specific features of educational tourism and types of educational tourism have been determined. The authors' definition of educational tourism as an economic category has been formulated. The authors' model of educational tourism, based on the notions of "education" and "tourism" has been developed. The most important prerequisites that determine the circumstances of the educational tourism market development have been characterized. The actual problems of educational tourism of Ukraine have been allocated. The ways for improving educational tourism of Ukraine and recommendations for improving this category of tourism have been developed.

Keywords: tourism, educational tourism, educational tourism market, factor, prospects, development

Educational tourism is one of the most popular types of travelling. The educational tourism recognition in Ukraine grows rapidly every year, and more people strive to get education in one of the most prestigious educational institutions in the world, to study or get internship abroad and to raise their intellectual and general education. Sometimes a little experience of being in a foreign environment can contribute to significant personal development.

Educational tourism actually appeared on the Earth a long time ago because the desire to acquire new knowledge was the aim of travelling for the overwhelming majority of travellers. Educational tourism is not about reducing its momentum, it is one of the most relevant and popular tourism in Ukraine and other countries.

Educational tourism is an important and perspective direction in cultural exchange, promotes integration and globalization of countries in international educational space. From other kinds of tourism educational purpose differs, i.e. receiving the education and tours duration.

The relevance of educational tourism in the modern world is conditioned by its effectiveness for teaching and educating the population of the country. But despite the active development of the tourist activity, so far there has not been developed a single opinion on interpretation of the educational tourism essence and its understandable apparatus.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

Significant contribution to the development of this topic was made by both domestic and foreign researchers and scientists, namely, V.V. Chernyshova, I.V. Davydenko, A.V. Babkin, N.A. Kozlova, V.Ya. Vatsaba, Ye. Kozlovskiy, O.O. Liubitseva, A.N. Kovalova, Greg Richards, Brent Ritchy,

Nikolas Kar, the research of this subject has been started in the works of the above mentioned scientists.

Allocation of previously unsolved parts of the general problem. When studying the educational tourism market development the attention should be paid to the main factors influencing the development of this type of tourism.

The aim of the article is to reveal the main factors for the educational tourism market development of Ukraine.

Methodological and informational bases of the research are scientific publications, works and researches of domestic and foreign scientists. The methods of comparison, analysis, generalization, system approach, etc. have been used in this scientific research.

The main part

To date, educational tourism is a priority type of tourism for young people and is an important part of the social and cultural activity of modern society. Tourists who travel for the educational purpose bring active social and economic changes that affect the educational services market.

At present, there is a gradual development of cooperation between Ukraine and the largest universities and scientific institutions in order to integrate Ukrainian education with the best foreign practices. The opportunity to improve, to receive education abroad, to learn the world have made educational tourism one of the informal types of education.

Among foreign studies, devoted to the mentioned type of tourism, one can distinguish the fundamental work of B. Ritchie (Brent W. Ritchie, 2003) "Managing Educational Tourism". The following definition is given in it: "Educational tourism is the activity of travellers, for which education and training is the main or secondary purpose of the trip". B. Ritchie divides educational tourism into two segments: "education first" and "tourism first". The segment "education first", to which the given researcher refers school excursions, studies in language schools and universities, provides a trip, the main purpose of which is education and training. In the "tourism first" segment, which includes cognitive or entertaining tourism, purposeful training is a secondary motive of a trip [1].

Educational tourism has arisen at the intersection of education and tourism, which in turn determines its dependence on the development of these economy sectors and consumer demands. Modern educational tourism is considered by science as an integrative product. As an innovative method, educational tourism contributes to students' activity, encourages them to independent creative work, initiative, inculcates skills and self-education skills, etc. Thus providing high-quality training of specialists capable of effective social self-realization.

Dynamic development of educational and tourist sectors has led to the emergence of educational tourism as a separate segment. Educational tourism combines the features of two spheres: education and tourism, which at the junction give own educational tourism (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The Educational Tourism Model

Source: authors' own development

The presented model of educational tourism shows the interrelation and integration of two non-distant areas: education and tourism. At the same time, the spheres division in educational tourism allows to judge that for some of its "consumers" the first place is the educational function, which is oriented on satisfaction of own needs, motives, goals and tasks. And for others – tourism together with its goals, objectives, motives, specific industry and tourist service.

Of course, education and tourism may seem to be incoherent at the first glance, but nevertheless they are perfectly combined, because when travelling abroad one can learn the language, culture, customs and traditions of the country. Research author Brent W. Ritchie (2003), argues that tourism as a whole expands the human circle, so many factors of tourism can be considered educational [1].

Therefore, most often to understand this category of tourism one distinguishes the following features of educational tourism:

- any trip during which a traveller is taught in any sphere;
- travelling in which education is the main value;
- revenues from educational tourism go to support the economy of the state;
- thanks to the educational tourism development new jobs are emerging.

It is also possible to allocate four main components of educational tourism (Table 1).

It is possible to see that in connection with globalization processes the interdependence of countries and people, their economic, social and cultural development in large measure begins to depend on the ability of the two branches, i.e. education and tourism in order to create conditions for support of

international exchange and training. The changes that have taken place over the last decades in the tourism industry and in the education system (the concept of

"lifelong learning") have contributed to the emergence of educational tourism in many countries.

Table 1. Main components of educational tourism

Educational tourism component	Characteristic
"Education"	In other words, travelling involves the presence of educational centres, new knowledge and skills acquisition by tourists
"Active rest"	It is meant that travelling is built in such a way that a person was not overloaded with study and could combine rest and study
"Respect for the local residents' interests"	Not only observing local laws and customs, but also contribution of tourism to socio-economic development of tourist destinations
"Support of local population"	For the majority of the island countries, educational tourism is practically the main source of income for local residents

Source: authors' own development

As for Ukraine, on the world market of educational tourism our state still acts as a recipient of educational and tourist ambassador. Thus, our fellow citizens still have little knowledge of attractive opportunities to combine study with a variety of additional pleasant and useful types of recreation [2].

If we talk about the basic motives of educational tourism, they can be:

- visiting cultural, scientific and technical institutions;
- evaluating art, music, literature and cultural heritage;
- study and research of individual countries,
- pleasure of his/her desire to travel;
- to be present at events of special interest;
- to see the way of life of other people, how they live and work, so to satisfy curiosity;
- to improve their knowledge, understanding and basing on the new that is in the world;
- visiting educational quest-tours, or quest-excursions, which satisfy professional, historical or cultural interest.

It is clear that today becomes an irrelevant system of education, in which a student only perceives information, engaged in passive position in the educational process. In Ukraine, new forms of educational processes are being actively introduced, in which students will feel on their own approaches aimed at developing in the students of organization, independence, ability to adapt to changes in society, learning, production, information systems. After all, the future specialists' skills in the respective profiles and training directions depend on the content and methodology of training.

It is worth noting the specific features of educational tourism, which are shown in:

- special demand;
- pronounced seasonal fluctuations;
- diversification of tourist product and hospitality services;
- but the most important thing is to understand and take into account that any trip should have an

educational factor. In every trip, even in a business trip, a person gets an impression and knowledge, mobilizes attention, thinking, memory, feels a lot of emotions, developing communication.

The modern sphere of educational tourism covers all types of education and training, which are carried out outside the permanent place of residence. Every year, the range of services offered in the direction of educational tourism is expanding rapidly. If a few years ago this type of tourism was demanded only among the elite, now it has moved into a product category for the middle class and is in constant demand of Ukrainian citizens.

At present there are several main types of educational tourism:

- guided tours to different cities, natural zones and settlements;
- educational tours on studying a foreign language or some general or special subjects;
- educational tours to organizations and enterprises;
- scientific and educational training in organizations and companies;
- participation in various seminars, conferences, congresses, master-classes, the purpose of which is to exchange experience and receive new important information.

Therefore, educational tourism should also be understood as a tourist trip, which is a trip to the place of temporary residence for the purpose of obtaining further knowledge, education and qualifications, which are carried out outside the place of residence. This type of tourism helps to form educational mobility and stimulates the self-educational skills development among the population.

Among the most important prerequisites that define the educational tourism market development the following can be identified [2]:

- international relations liberalization and geographical space compression;
- globalization of the world information space promotes the increasing amount of information

- available for mastering by a modern person, creating a fruitful basis for self-development;
- the establishment of English as the language of international communication has allowed to increase the communicability of modern civilization sharply. Knowledge of English is a necessary condition of self-development and successful career;
- the spread of mass culture and the unification of the requirements for professional excellence opens up opportunities for modern people to be realized in any country of the world. The desire to access the

- best education and to constantly expand their knowledge is especially relevant for the inhabitants of developing countries and post-socialist countries in light of the policy of "brain suction", which is carried out by developed countries;
- the life style intensification makes it possible to use time as efficiently as possible, stimulating the practice of combining rest and training.

Thus, the main factors that influence the educational tourism market development in Ukraine and the world are listed in the Table 2.

Table 2. Factors that influence the educational tourism market development in Ukraine and the world

Factor	Characteristic
Scientific and technical progress	The rapid development of a powerful material and technical base of international tourism
Demographic factors	Population growth of our planet. For example, the increase in average life expectancy in many countries is the reason that more people have free time and money. This allows them to make international travel
Social factors	It is necessary to increase the population's welfare of developed countries
Cultural factors	The growing cultural level among the population of many countries, and in this connection people's aspiration to familiarize with foreign cultural values
International factors	Mitigating the international climate, the transition from confrontation between the leading countries to cooperation and understanding, and resolving controversial international issues through the negotiation process

Source: authors' own development

Constantly acting factors in a certain period may increase or decrease various smaller and short-term changes, whose consideration is also included in the marketing research tasks [3].

Educational tourism in all its diversity is a phenomenon, but it is still not enough mass. However, in light of the current dynamics of the world economy development and liberalization of the sphere of international relations, the popularity of "useful rest" has grown considerably.

But there are some obstacles that hinder the educational tourism market development:

- little study and potential cannot be fully evaluated;
- there is a fairly high price. This is reflected in the fact that educational tourism is accessible to a certain group of population;
- despite the fact that foreign education is considered prestigious, there are opinions that speak not in its favour and may hinder the educational tourism development. For example, universities in Spain and Italy have a very large number of students in groups, which does not contribute to improving the efficiency of the educational process;
- in many countries the most popular languages for study are English, Italian, Spanish, German and French. Accordingly, educational tourism in these countries is more intensively developing than in others.

Thus, the main problems of the educational tourism market development of Ukraine can be identified:

- low-cost tourist and educational infrastructure;

- the unformed image of Ukraine as a tourist educational establishment;

- absence of a wide range of competitive tourist products;

- lack of qualified personnel in the tourism industry.

A global problem is also the impact on educational tourism the COVID-19 pandemic. Of course, in these conditions it is impossible to travel abroad and back for a number of reasons, the most important of which are:

- the possibility of infection;
- closing of tourist borders;
- closing of most cultural sites and monuments;
- ban on mass events (lectures) etc.

Under the unfavourable epidemiological situation, the educational tourism business development was under serious threat. According to experts, only in the first months of the pandemic, demand for all travel directions fell by 20-25%, and after the borders closure by many countries it fell to almost zero. Educational tourism suffered the most. After a month-long closure of borders due to the COVID-19 pandemic, educational tourism is experiencing an unseen crisis [4].

Many educational tourist programmes have been canceled and transferred to the next year. Some travel companies have started offering virtual educational tours.

Before making forecasts for the educational tourism development, it is possible to notice that, despite the existing problems, there are factors that contribute to its development, namely:

- the people's mentality is changing, especially in Ukraine, the interest of young people in education is noted. Getting higher education becomes not only prestigious, but also necessary, because people are increasingly interested in the professions connected with mental work, as well as growing interest in international culture. A person has become more purposeful, she needs knowledge and experience of work for improvement of qualification in a certain sphere;
- improving the modern educational system, as our system is on the way of development and has differences from the European education.

Therefore, the prospects of educational tourism can be considered:

- raising the cultural level;
- people's aspiration to knowledge, acquaintance with life, culture and the intentions of other countries and peoples;
- foreign economic relations development, attracting people to communication and use of experience of other countries in creation of material and spiritual values find reflection in strengthening the scientific and business contacts, the manifestation of which is development of new types of international tourism relations, i.e. scientific (congress) and business tourism [5].

It is worth noting that the educational tourism development contributes to the partnership relations development between Ukraine and foreign countries. That is why knowledge of a foreign language, management knowledge and administration is very necessary for doing business. We believe that these positive factors will contribute to the active development of educational tourism in the nearest future.

We offer the following measures for improving the educational tourism market of Ukraine:

- formulation of the rational planning policy;

- location of tourist infrastructure facilities;
- modernization of existing accommodation facilities for students;
- creating accessible places of public catering for students;
- creating a transport cycle frame, special preferential routes for students;
- creating the universities bases of Ukraine of the European "Student Services" analogues for eliminating the intercultural barrier and providing foreign students with the fastest adaptation in the city;
- personnel training for educational tourism as the main factor of development in Ukraine.

Conclusions

After all, educational tourism (both national and international) is an important and promising area of social activity that affects both the Ukrainian tourism development and the Ukrainian educational system improvement.

After all, it is impossible to imagine humanity without travelling. Currently, a huge flow of various knowledge passes through human consciousness. From oversaturation with different information flows, an individual gets tired, not having time to structure the acquired knowledge, ceases to perceive new information. The acquired knowledge is gradually forgotten and lost.

Despite this, the knowledge gained during the journey, almost forever remain in our memory. This is due to the fact that positive emotions force a person to experience this period again and again. Thus, educational tourism can stimulate society to further development.

Promising aspects of this work can be considered the selection of the main factors influencing the educational tourism market development of Ukraine and the measures development in order to improve the educational tourism market of Ukraine.

Abstract

The presented model of educational tourism demonstrates the interconnection and integration of two incompatible areas: education and tourism. At the same time, the spheres delimitation in educational tourism allows us to judge that for the individual "consumers" in the first place comes directly with an educational function, focused on satisfaction of their own needs, incentives, goals and objectives. And for others – tourism with its goals, tasks, incentives, specific industry and a tourist service. It can be seen that in connection with the globalization processes, the interdependence of countries and peoples increases, their economic, social and cultural development is largely beginning to depend on the ability of two branches, i.e. education and tourism to create conditions for supporting international exchange and training. It is clear that today it becomes an inacceptable education system in which a student only perceives information, taking a passive position in the educational process. In Ukraine, active introduction of new forms of educational processes organization, in which students will experience approaches that are aimed at developing organism students, autonomy, ability to adapt to changes in society, training, production, information systems. After all, the content and methodology of learning depend on the skills of future specialists in the relevant profiles and directions of study. In an unfavorable epidemiological situation, the development of educational tourism business was under serious threat. According to experts, only in the first months of the pandemic demand for all outbound directions decreased by 20-25%, and after closing borders by many states – fell almost zero. The educational tourism was most affected. Summing up, we can say that educational tourism (both national and international) is an important and promising area of social activity that affects both the development of Ukrainian tourism and improvement of the Ukrainian education system.

After all, it is impossible to imagine humanity without travel. Currently, due to the consciousness of a person passes a huge flow of diverse knowledge. From the saturation of various information flow, an individual is tired,

without having time to structure acquired knowledge, ceases to perceive new information. The acquired knowledge is gradually forgotten and are lost. Despite this knowledge gained in the process of travel, practically forever remain in our memory. This is due to the fact that positive emotions force a person to experience this period again and again.

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